

Coronavirus Disease Research Community – COVID-19

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Title: **Forecast of COVID19 infections, USA**

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I have updated the COVID19 infections data and forecast in USA on May 10th, publishing the graphs on the following free blog:

<https://covid19forecast.blogspot.com/>

<https://usacovid19.blogspot.com/>

The same figures are reported here.

The forecast of the total positive cases, according to the Verhulst equation, is over 1,450,000 cases, with a ratio per 1000 capita of 4.4, while the forecast of the total deaths is over 88,000.

The forecast of the new cases is showing the trend to decrease.